

ADvanced MultImodal maRketplAce for Low emission and energy transportation – ADMIRAL

Addressing Corporate Sustainable

Development Reporting Directive (CSRD)

21st International Conference on Transport
Science – ICTS 2024
May 2024, Porotož

Blaž Luin, Patricija Bajec,
Vivien Lorenčič, Marina Zanne,
Danijela Tuljak-Suban,
Elen Twrdy

FPP

UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
Fakulteta za pomorstvo in promet

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contents

- Emissions are the key.
- What is a digital marketplace?
- Why ADMIRAL marketplace?
- ADMIRAL marketplace (partners, functionalities, competitive differentiation)
- How ADMIRAL marketplace will be developed?

World Energy Outlook

Energija - Svet porablja 18 TW (2019 www.bp.com. 7.7 milijard ljudi)

~60 kWh/dan/osebo (2019) (točna številka =58 po BP)

Big differences between countries

Energy use per person, 2022

Measured in kilowatt-hours per person. Here, energy refers to primary energy using the substitution method.

Table Map Chart

World

Play time-lapse

1965

Emissions overview

- Transport represents nearly a third of worldwide energy consumption
- We are on the way to decarbonization
 - Tackling global warming

Total final energy consumption, World, 2021

Source: International Energy Agency. Licence: CC BY 4.0

Emissions overview

Global primary energy consumption by source

Primary energy is based on the substitution method and measured in terawatt-hours.

Our World
in Data

Table Chart

Settings

1800 2022

Data source: Energy Institute - Statistical Review of World Energy (2023); Smil (2017) - [Learn more about this data](#)

Note: In the absence of more recent data, traditional biomass is assumed constant since 2015.

OurWorldInData.org/energy | CC BY

Electricity consumption per capita

↑46%

change 2000-2021

[Electricity](#)

Energy intensity of the economy

↓26%

change 2000-2021

[Efficiency & demand](#)

Renewables

24.7%

share of power generation, 2021

[Renewables](#)

Oil

29%

of total energy supply, 2021

[Oil](#)

Natural gas production

↑70%

change 2000-2021

[Natural gas](#)

Coal

27%

of total energy supply, 2021

[Coal](#)

Emissions overview

What is digital marketplace?

This is a cloud-based digital platform that simplifies the **connection between supply and demand** by bringing together various actors in the supply chain, such as **cargo owners** seeking suitable providers of logistics services and **logistics and transport providers** that offer logistics services.

Source: <https://www.timocom.si/>, <https://www.transporeon.com/en>

Major players

Table 1. Comparison between Timocom and Transporeon

	<u>Timocom</u>	<u>Transporeon</u>
Established	1997	2000
Offering	Freight and vehicle space exchange, transport directory, calculation tools for route and transport costs; around 1 million freight and vehicle offer daily	Transportation management, freight procurement, and time slot management for docks and yards
Sellers	55,000 transport service providers 9,000 warehousing and logistics spaces across 46 European countries	1,400+ connected shippers, 158,000+ carriers, and 100+ retailers
Customers	More than 155,000 users, primarily from the European logistics sector	Predominantly from Europe, but also from Asia and Americas
Pricing policy	A variety of pricing plans	Free for shippers, EUR 100 per month for carriers
Revenues	EUR 90 million in 2022	EUR 190 million in 2023

Source: <https://www.timocom.si/>, <https://www.transporeon.com/en>

EU directive (CSRD 2022/2464/EN)

Upstream and downstream activities

Why ADMIRAL marketplace?

- currently focus on SCOPE 1 and SCOPE 2, BUT NOT SCOPE 3 emissions,
- Upcoming EU directive (CSRD 2022/2464/EU) demands large companies to report their SCOPE 3 emissions from 2025,
- from 2028 all companies operating within the European Union will be required to report SCOPE 3 emissions
- Currently no digital logistics marketplace offers SCOPE 3 emissions predictions or calculations.
(e.g. Timocom & similar platforms)

Source: <https://www.nationalgrid.com/stories/energy-explained/what-are-scope-1-2-3-carbon-emissions>

ADMIRAL marketplace

- Currently scope 3 emissions produced by the supply chain have not been in focus of companies.
- The incoming EU regulations demand large companies to report their scope 3 emissions.
- This will be extended gradually to cover all the companies operating inside EU by 2028.
- Means to reliably measure, calculate, combine and report these emissions is increasingly needed.
- ADMIRAL project is building an emissions-aware marketplace for logistics services.
- One key capability is to compile Scope 3 emissions data from multimodal logistics chains, enabling cargo owners to select the most emissions efficient transportation alternatives.
- The marketplace also connects IT developers and integrators to develop the services further, forming an ecosystem to promote the goal towards a carbon-neutral world.

ADMIRAL marketplace-PARTNERS

MARKETPLACE.AWAKE.AI

ADMIRAL STAKEHOLDERS COLLABORATIVE FORUM

ADMIRAL is open to any stakeholder involved or interested in greening the supply chain, such as cargo owners, logistics services providers, infrastructure managers and operators, energy supplies, governments, academia, etc.

By joining the Forum, your organization will:

- Be invited to **large-scale** events, workshops and e-training activities **in the framework of the project**
- Provide feedback about innovations **aimed at greening the supply chain**
- Get at the forefront of the upcoming EU regulation on reporting GHG emissions, especially Scope 3
- Co-design ADMIRAL's business models, **digital marketplace, roadmaps and policy recommendations**

JOIN THE STAKEHOLDERS'
COLLABORATIVE FORUM

ADMIRAL marketplace-VALUE PROPOSITIONS

SELLERS:

Slash customer acquisition costs! Gain EU-wide visibility instantly.

Elevate revenue with eco-friendly equipment. Showcase reduced emissions transparently, outshine the competition.

Boost revenue by tapping into multi-country, multimodal cargo routes. Expand your reach and profits

Skyrocket customer satisfaction! Streamline purchases with efficient tools and transparent cargo insights.

Expand effortlessly! Unlock new routes and services with reduced costs.

BUYERS:

Stay green with informed choices! Easily switch to lower-emission logistics options for a sustainable business.

Receive post-transport emissions calculations for comprehensive reporting at your fingertips.

Simplify logistics! Source all your multimodal, multi-country transport needs in one convenient platform.

Supercharge your purchases! Rapid, intelligent buying handles more needs with fewer resources.

Stay in control! Track your cargo seamlessly and resolve issues faster with our efficient system.

Source: AWAKE.AI

DATA & SERVICE SELLERS FOR THE MARKETPLACE ENGINE:

Unlock revenue streams! Offer services like equipment visibility and emissions calculators, trading valuable data within the Marketplace.

Seize new opportunities! Identify data and service gaps, then leverage the Marketplace platform to pioneer innovative solutions.

Elevate your solutions! Access valuable data from the Marketplace to enhance and build more sophisticated offerings.

INTEGRATORS:

Seamless integration, limitless possibilities! Harness Marketplace APIs for one or two-way integrations, enabling buying and selling within your 3rd party solutions.

Innovate effortlessly! Construct new solutions or enhance existing ones with the power of rich Marketplace APIs.

Collaborate for success! Partner with Awake.AI, the Marketplace operator, to co-create additional capabilities, addressing valuable business needs.

Source: AWAKE.AI

ADMIRAL marketplace-COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES

Emissions Awareness

Purchase with eco-consciousness. Receive emissions report upon fulfillment.

Basic & Complex Services

Access 100+ services seamlessly connected to maritime ports, land hubs, and warehouses.

Intermodal & Multimodal Shipping

Explore European routes with diverse equipment options across multiple countries.

Neutral Operator

Awake.AI operates neutrally, gaining benefits only when both buyers and sellers prosper.

AI Predictions

AI predictions for arrivals of sea and land equipment, along with emissions and warnings.

AI Working with Humans

AI supports humans with suggestions and advanced warnings, with humans always making the final decisions.

Open API Platform

Connect and innovate with new solutions. Deliver data and digital services.

Powerful Developer Experience

Explore our extensive developer portal featuring documentation, examples, and discussions. Obtain your API key in just 1 minute.

Source: AWAKE.AI

General project information and partners presentation

Project name: Advanced multimodal marketplace for low emission and energy transportation

Project acronym: ADMIRAL

Duration: 36 months, 1.5.2023 – 30.4.2026

Partners: 20 beneficiaries, 1 affiliated entity

Coordinator: VTT

Max. EU contribution: 7 294 412,14 €

Granting authority: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)

21 organisations coming from 9 different European countries

WP1 Project management

Ensures the overall management, administration, coordination and execution of the project.

WP2 Sustainability development

Addresses key sustainability issues in the transport and logistics sector, such as low emissions, fossil fuels energy reduction and enhancement of collaborative logistics to reach common sustainability goals in the pilots.

WP4 Development of technical solutions

Develops the marketplace for multimodal, emissions aware and optimizing logistics and scale the AI driven trading & routing to multiple logistic chains globally.

WP5 Pilots

Coordinates the Pilots, provides case contexts to WP2 & 3 analyses and tests and demonstrates the developed models and solutions from WPs 2-4.

WP6 Assessment of results

Assesses the impacts of ADMIRAL solutions. Overall impact assessment considering real-life demonstrations.

WP3 Business models

Innovates, develops and demonstrates potential new collaborative governance practices and business models based on research studies and all pilots and emerged cooperation competence skills and AI platform related functionalities.

WP7 Dissemination, communications and exploitation

Communicates and disseminates the ADMIRAL vision, activities and results. Enhances exploitation by stimulating early uptake and technology adoption, and seeks to build an engaged ecosystem around the project.

Methodology

The ADMIRAL marketplace will be developed through:

- 4 pilots in Portugal-Spain, Slovenia-Croatia, Lithuania and Finland representing a variety of use cases from port operators to postal logistics and road transport services &
- application of AI technologies for process optimization and emission monitoring &
- with each pilot contributing one or more advanced services or solutions to the marketplace.

Pilot: Slovenia, Croatia

Current situation

Pilot Slovenia, Croatia

Pilot Finland

- **Stevec** Group provides full logistic services from production to final destinations: **stevedoring, forwarding, customs-, transport- and terminal services.**
- terminals at the ports of Kotka, Helsinki, Hamina and lake Saimaa area.

Pilot, Finland, KPIs

Pilot Finland, KPIs

Pilot goals – what we aim at

- Unloading time of truck or train will be reduced by 15% in port
- Current warehouses allow passage of 15% more cargo
- Current stevedore workers and port equipment can handle 20% more cargo in a same time in the operations of unloading truck or train, warehousing, and loading a vessel.
- Due to higher productivity, emissions of working machines will be reduced by approx. 15%

Metrics – what our AI will directly optimize

- Average loaded driving distance per ton of cargo, m/ton.
- Average number of times each cargo package is moved, dimensionless.
- Average handling time per ton of cargo, min/ton.
- Warehouse capacity utilization, tons of cargo stored per allocated warehouse area, ton/m².
- Transport unit capacity utilization, tons of cargo per transport unit hour, ton/unit·h.

Expected Impacts

- Validated ADMIRAL multimodal low-emission marketplace.
- Optimised logistics processes, resulting in time and cost savings.
- 20 % emission reduction in transport and logistics through process optimization.
- Enhanced stakeholder cooperation and supply chain resilience.
- Stronger emphasis on emission reductions in the logistics and transport industry
- Business models for low-emission transport chains.

Selected route: Zwevegem– Milano –Turin – Zwevegem

Inland freight route Zwevegem – Milano –Turin – Zwevegem is used as a baseline to evaluate CO2 emissions and identify possible improvements.

For regular operation, Switzerland is avoided due to complex transit requirements and alternative route results in extra mileage;

While this decision is driven by business goals, it may have greater environmental impact due to increased CO2 emissions;

More sustainable solution is needed that is both sensible for business and contributes towards environmental goals.

Refresher – Lithuanian pilot goals

CO2 calculations

Understanding current landscape of software used to optimize routes and calculate CO2 emissions (what is used, to what extent, why certain solutions are favored over others, what data is collected, data structures and volumes, what motivation is needed for broader data exchanges)

Data exchange

Defining data exchange needs, structures and technical solutions for data and information exchange (eg. APIs)

Digital integration

Identifying the most efficient, secure and resource-efficient solutions for integrations between different digital tools

Testing

Developing and testing data exchange solutions and testing in relevant environment (pilot logistics network and Multimodal Marketplace) with network participants (freight operators, freight forwarders, IT solution providers, transport hubs, warehouses, etc.)

Business models

Defining business models and motivations for broader adoption of fleet management and CO2 emission calculation tools in logistics companies.

Thank you for your attention!

